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Translation of Business Process Model and Notation
into Integrated Model of Distributed Systems

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Abstract

Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) is a tool to describe business processes using convenient diagrams. In the last decade, it became a *de-facto* industry standard, widely used by software architects and business analysts to describe business requirements and the overall structure of a designed information system. Unfortunately, the authors of the notation did not provide any formal framework to verify correctness of BPMN diagrams. Ensuring that the diagrams model the intended behavior is of utmost importance to the users of the notation. This thesis deals with detection of possible deadlocks on BPMN diagrams. Formal syntax and semantics for a chosen subset of the notation are defined and a method of verification of BPMN diagrams using Integrated Model of Distributed Systems (IMDS) is proposed. Integrated Model of Distributed Systems is a formalism to model distributed systems, developed at Institute of Computer Science, Warsaw University of Technology. The goal of the thesis is to develop an automatic tool that enables verification of BPMN diagrams and visualization of counterexample leading to the revealed deadlocks in a step-by-step manner.

Key words: BPMN, model checking, IMDS, business processes, verification

Translacja modelu biznesowego BPMN do formalizmu IMDS

Streszczenie

Model biznesowy BPMN (ang. *Business Process Model and Notation*) to narzędzie służące do opisu procesów biznesowych przy pomocy wygodnych diagramów. W ostatniej dekadzie stało się ono standardem przemysłowym, powszechnie używanym przez architektów oprogramowania i analityków biznesowych do opisu wymagań biznesowych i ogólnej architektury projektowanego systemu informatycznego. Autorzy notacji nie dostarczyli żadnych narzędzi do weryfikacji poprawności diagramów BPMN. Weryfikacja, czy dany diagram prawidłowo modeluje zachowanie systemu ma niebagatelne znaczenia dla użytkowników notacji. Niniejsza praca traktuje o wykrywaniu możliwych zakleszczeń w diagramach BPMN. Praca zawiera formalizację składni i semantyki wybranego podzbioru BPMN oraz proponuje metodę sprawdzania poprawności diagramów zapisanych w tej notacji, używając formalizmu IMDS (ang. *Integrated Model of Distributed Systems*). Formalizm IMDS opracowany został w Instytucie Informatyki Politechniki Warszawskiej i służy do specyfikacji systemów rozproszonych. W ramach pracy wykonany został program weryfikujący diagramy BPMN i wizualizujący kontrprzykłady prowadzące do zakleszczeń.

Słowa kluczowe: BPMN, weryfikacja modelowa, IMDS, procesy biznesowe, weryfikacja

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1 Introduction

1.1 Business processes as a means of work management in organizations

Business processes are a set of activities in organizations, such as corporations or institutions, whose aim is to accomplish a certain goal, desired by the client or by the organization itself. Such goals are for example provided products or executed services.

An example of business processes in everyday life is ordering of a product in an online shop. Relevant steps of such a business process include:

- client fills up the online form, ordering the product,
- vendor receives request, sends back data for bank transfer to the client,
- client transfers money to the vendor,
- vendor receives money and ships the order to the client,
- order is received by the client.

Desired characteristics of business processes includes preservation of logical relationship between each of the preceding and the following activities, efficiency – ie. once executed, they should be accomplished as soon as possible, reliability – in that they should finish with the expected result etc.

Business processes should also coordinate work between different stakeholders of the workflow. They may involve different departments within the organization, for example customer support, sales, human resources, marketing etc. Synchronization between those entities is an important aspect of every business process.

Additionally, modern business processes should also be digitalized, that is they should be supported by appropriate software which should act as a framework in which they are defined and then executed. Digital business processes should also be fault-tolerant, ie. they should properly handle any errors that occur, and they should always finish in stable state.

Business processes have solid theoretical foundations in *workflow nets*[1] – a class of Petri nets[2] that is intended to model business behavior of systems. Thus, business processes can be formally analyzed in mathematical terms.

Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), introduced by BPMP & iGrafx in 2004 [3], is a graphical framework to model business processes using convenient graphical notation. Its current version – 2.0.2 – has been developed by Object Management Group[4]. The official specification consists of around 100 symbols which represent different aspects of process execution, communication between stakeholders, dataflow, etc. BPMN 2.0.x has found a wide range of applications in commercial use. There exists a growing community of developers, enterprises and applications that develop and support tools implementing BPMN. In total, there are around 70 major tools that enable to model, execute and maintain processes defined in BPMN[5].

XML has been chosen as the file format in which BPMN models are represented. The BPMN XML schema defines types to describe participants and their workflow in a process. It also describes

collaborations between participants, ie. how they communicate using messages, in which order messages should be exchanged etc. Diagrams in BPMN XML format use *.bpmn* file extension.

From now on we use the word *model* and *diagram* interchangeably to mean a business process written in BPMN.

1.2 Motivation of the thesis - verification of Business Process Model and Notation

Proper modelling has become an important step during design of business processes. Finding and correcting possible flaws in the model at the design time can save up money and time during its implementation and later – maintenance. *Temporal verification of BPMN* is the process of ensuring that a given business process written in BPMN does follow its intended behavior. *Temporal verification* is done using *model checking* – a method of expressing the given BPMN diagram in a formal language and then asserting that certain properties hold with respect to possible execution traces of the modelled process using temporal logic – for instance Linear Temporal Logic[6].

This thesis deals with detection of *deadlocks*, ie. situations in which execution of a given business process designed falls into such a state, that the system as a whole or its parts will not progress anymore.

A major problem that remains unsolved is that Business Process Model and Notation includes a very rich syntax of BPMN elements, yet it lacks proper formalization of their semantics[7]. This problem has been widely addressed in the literature due to its impact on verification of BPMN in terms of correctly expressing all relevant properties of the given model in a formal language. Because BPMN elements semantics is in some cases non-local (most notable examples include *Inclusive Gateways*), it is often hard to formalize it in a rigorous way.

This thesis proposes a method of mapping of BPMN into *Integrated Model of Distributed Systems (IMDS)*[8]. *IMDS* is a formalism to describe distributed computational systems introduced by S. Chrobot and W. Daszczuk in 2006. Its idea is based on the observation that any distributed computation can be either regarded as a sequence of exchanged messages or as sequence of changes of its components' states.

The most interesting property of IMDS that is extensively used in this paper is the ability to discover *partial deadlocks* in the examined model. *Partial deadlock* is a situation in which the system can overall progress, but there is a subset of its elements that will remain blocked. A partial deadlock in a BPMN diagram manifests itself with possibility of not being able to execute some activities because the diagram is structurally invalid. Activities on the diagram that may not be executed at all in the modelled business process are clearly a modeling error in that they are either redundant or the model doesn't follow the intended behavior. Thus, detecting *partial deadlocks* is of great use during design of business processes

1.3 Research problem

This paper has two major goals:

1. proposing a translation method BPMN into IMDS; moreover, determination what impact do the concepts that Integrated Model of Distributed Systems introduces have on deadlock detection in BPMN,
2. implementation of an automatic tool to verify BPMN that will be able to load a .bpmn file, visualize the input, verify whether the given model contains a deadlock and – if that is the case – mark the path that leads to it.

The first motivation comes from the fact that Integrated Model of Distributed Systems is a fairly new academic formalism in the field of distributed systems verification. An ongoing research on IMDS aims to verify what kind of distributed systems the formalism can cope with. BPMN seems to be an interesting subject to research about IMDS due to its common usage and expressiveness. This thesis tries to answer the question what limitations a possible translation of BPMN into IMDS does have.

The second motivation comes from a plain practical point and aims to ultimately develop a convenient automatic analyzer of BPMN Process and Collaboration diagrams. There are many publications about verification of BPMN using different kinds of formalisms, but few of them actually present a working solution that can be used to verify real-life use cases of BPMN diagrams.

1.4 Structure of the document

The first section presents the background of the research problem and the structure of the document. The second section presents related work in the field of BPMN verification and semantics definition. The third section defines formal syntax and semantics of IMDS and BPMN. The fourth section proposes a method of translation of the chosen subset of BPMN into IMDS. In the fifth section examples to that method are presented. In the sixth section, the architecture of the tool *bpmn2imds* is described. The seventh section deals with tests and benchmarks executed in that tool. In the eight section conclusions and future work are discussed.

2 Related work

Multiple techniques of BPMN formalization have been proposed. A common way of doing it is to map BPMN into Petri nets. Paper [9] proposes a mapping into *classic* Petri nets. It deals with a concise subset of BPMN, containing BPMN elements with local semantics, including Pools, Sub-processes, Exclusive Gateways, Parallel Gateways, Event-Based Gateways, Tasks, Events and exception handling, whereas Tasks with only a single outgoing or incoming Message Flow are considered. The authors also implemented a tool to transform BPMN diagrams into a Petri Net Markup Language specification[10] that can be further processed by Petri net verifier. Although the paper deals with translation only of BPMN 1.x diagrams, it gives a general idea how a mapping of BPMN 2.0.x into Petri nets could look like.

Paper [11] proposes a mapping into *time* Petri Nets. The considered subset is the same as in [9] but the mapping introduces time constraints on execution of BPMN elements. The authors propose an algorithm for the reachability analysis of the resulting TPN, but do not provide an automatic tool.

Authors of [12] propose a mapping of BPMN into *colored* Petri nets. Additionally, they introduce a method to divide a given BPMN model into partitions and verify them hierarchically, which reduces complexity of the resulting colored Petri net model. Unfortunately, the method works only for BPMN model that are *well-defined*, that is, only for a relatively small subset of BPMN, which limits its expressiveness. Additionally, the authors have implemented a tool that automatically translates BPMN diagrams into the corresponding colored Petri net.

Paper [13] proposes another method of mapping BPMN into *classic* Petri nets. The method is rather poorly described and can be applied to only small subset of BPMN, but it introduces the concept of *preprocessing* of BPMN diagrams. A similar concept, called *normalization*, is a part of the BPMN-to-IMDS translation method, proposed in this thesis.

Other attempts to formalize BPMN include for example transformation of BPMN into Pi-Calculus [14], PROMELA [15], COWS [16] and YAWL[17].

As far as automatic verification of BPMN is concerned, a reference point to this thesis is the *BProVe* program [18][19]. It enables verification of diagrams in terms of safeness, proper termination, dead activities among others. Its underlying logic is based on a translation of BPMN into MAUDE – a rewriting logic implementation. The solution is based on a web service. Another automatic tool, called VBPMN[20], uses a translation of BPMN into LOTOS NT formal notation together with verification using the CDAP verifier. Its authors provide also a set of benchmarks [21] that will be used during tests of the automatic tool proposed in this thesis.

3 IMDS and BPMN

3.1 Introduction to IMDS

IMDS formalism addresses parallel processes modeling. Its main idea is to show interactions between the three following concepts: servers, agents and actions.

Figure 1. An example of an IMDS model written as a Mealy automaton.

IMDS models can be graphically written down using Mealy automata like the one given on the Figure 1. This minimal example shows all the important concepts of IMDS. The given model consists of:

- a *server* that can with three *states*: {0, 1, 2}, that is providing three *services*: {compute, wait, save};
- one *agent*,
- four *messages*: (agent, server, save), (agent, server, compute), (agent, server, wait), (agent, -, -).

There are also three *actions* implicitly defined in this model:

- if the server is in the state 0 and there is a pending (agent, server, compute) message then the server can change its state to 1 and emit the message (agent, server, wait),
- if the server is in state 1 and there is a pending (agent, server, wait) message then the server can change its state to 2 and emit the message (agent, server, save),
- if the server is in the state 2 and there is a pending (agent, server, save) message then the server can change its state to 0 and emit *agent terminating message* (agent, -, -). Please note that a precise description of terminating action follows in the next paragraph.

3.2 Formal definition of IMDS

Formal definition of Integrated Model of Distributed Systems is presented below. Definitions of *servers*, *server states*, *servers' services*, *agents*, *messages*, *actions*, and interactions between them are followed by mathematical notation used in IMDS. In the end of this subsection, a formal definition of an IMDS model is given. For more information about IMDS, please refer to [8].

Definition 1. IMDS server (short: *server*) is a tuple (n, V, Q) , where: n – servers name, V – set of possible servers' states, Q – set of services available at the given server.

Definition 2. Servers' state (short: *servers state*) is a pair (s, v) , where s – server (n, V, Q) , $v \in V$.

Definition 3. IMDS agent (short: *agent*) is an entity that calls services on servers.

Servers services are executed in a sequential manner, one at a time. To execute a service, a message has to be sent to the server and the server needs to be in the state in which the server can accept the message. The relation between the server's state and the message that can be accepted in this state is called matching. Messages are defined by:

- agent that is the sender of the message,
- server that is the target of the message,
- service which the agent wants to be executed.

Definition 4. IMDS message (short: *message*) is a tuple: (a, s, q) , where a – agent, s – server (s, V, Q) and $q \in Q$.

Definition 5. Message (a, s, q) with both values s and q empty called *terminating message*.

Terminating message $(a, -, -)$ means, that the agent a has been terminated. Terminating message is denoted $(a, -, -)$ and its point is to explicitly show that the message neither has a target server, nor a target service. An agent that has terminated cannot be reinstated.

Definition 6. IMDS action is an element of the relation $\rightarrow \subset (K, S) \times (K, S)$, where K is the set of messages, S is the set of server states. \rightarrow relation means that if a given IMDS server s_1 is in the state (s_1, v_1) and there is a message of the form (a, s_1, q_1) is pending on it then the server may *accept* this message and next change its state to (s_1, v_2) , emitting the message (a, s_2, q_2) to the server s_2 . Execution of an *action* is atomic, ie. absorption of the input message, state change on the server and the emission of the output message happen at the same time.

Action of agent a , that is calling service q_1 on server s_1 , that changes the servers state from v_1 to v_2 and emits the output message that calls service q_2 on server s_2 is denoted:

$$((a, s_1, q_1), (s_1, v_1) \rightarrow (a, s_2, q_2)(s_1, v_2))$$

In particular, both messages in an action must be defined for the same agent and both server states must be defined for the same server. Please note that it is possible that the initial and the final states of

the server may stay the same. In this case the server doesn't change its state. Also, source and target servers of the action may stay the same, in which case the server sends a message to itself during execution of the action.

Each server is characterized by its *initial state* that is given at the beginning of systems simulation. Analogously, each agent is characterized by its *initial message*, which is the first message that exists in the system at the beginning of simulation. Because execution of any action absorbs exactly one message and emits exactly one, each agent will always have exactly one pending message in the system.

To make the notation more concise, the following denotes an action defined for a set of agents.

$$\begin{aligned} & ((A, s_1, q_1), (s_1, v_1) \rightarrow (A, s_2, q_2), (s_1, v_2)) \\ & \underset{\text{denotes}}{=} \{ e_i \in \rightarrow \mid a_i \in A \wedge e_i = ((a_i, s_1, q_1), (s_1, v_1) \rightarrow (a_i, s_2, q_2), (s_1, v_2)) \} \end{aligned}$$

In a given IMDS sets of *agents* and *servers* are static, ie. new cannot be created dynamically.

Definition 7. IMDS system is a tuple $(S, A, M_{init}, R_{init}, F)$, where:

- S is the set of *servers*,
- A is the set of *agents*,
- M_{init} is the set of *initial states* of servers from S ,
- R_{init} is the set of *initial messages* for agents from A ,
- F is the set of *actions* defined on S and A .

Definition 8. Initial state of IMDS system $(S, A, M_{init}, R_{init}, F)$ is the pair (M_{init}, R_{init}) .

After introducing formal concepts of IMDS we are ready to explicitly define the model from Figure 1 in formal terms as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (S, A, M_{init}, R_{init}, F) & := (\\ S & := \{(\text{server}, \{0, 1, 2\}, \{\text{compute}, \text{wait}, \text{save}\})\}, \\ A & := \{\text{agent}\}, \\ M_{init} & := \{(\text{server}, 0)\}, \\ R_{init} & := \{(\text{server}, \text{agent}, \text{compute})\}, \\ F & := \{((\text{agent}, \text{server}, \text{compute}), (\text{server}, 0) \rightarrow (\text{agent}, \text{server}, \text{wait}), (\text{server}, 1)), \\ & ((\text{agent}, \text{server}, \text{wait}), (\text{server}, 0) \rightarrow (\text{agent}, \text{server}, \text{wait}), (\text{server}, 2)), \\ & ((\text{agent}, \text{server}, \text{save}), (\text{server}, 0) \rightarrow (\text{agent}, -, -), (\text{server}, 2))\} \end{aligned}$$

3.3 Business Process Model and Notation

In general, the Business Process Model and Notation standard introduces four types of diagrams[4]:

1. Process Diagrams,
2. Collaboration Diagrams,
3. Choreography Diagrams,

4. Conversation Diagrams.

This paper deals with verification of Process Diagrams and Collaboration Diagrams. Choreography Diagrams and Conversation Diagrams are fully out of scope of this paper.

Process and Collaboration Diagrams describe control flow of a business process. They use five types of elements: *Swimlanes*, *Flow Objects*, *Data Objects*, *Connecting Objects* and *Artifacts*. This thesis deals primarily with verification consisting of *Swimlanes*, *Connecting Objects* and *Flow Objects*. *Data Objects* – elements that describe data flow in business processes are fully out of scope of this paper. *Artefacts* – elements that play explanatory role to the end user of Process Diagrams, like labels, text annotations, groups etc. – can be a part of the verified diagram, but they don't carry any semantical meaning as far as deadlock verification is concerned[7]. The only Artifacts that could be considered during verification are *compensation handlers* but BPMN's compensation mechanism is also out of scope of this thesis.

The authors of BPMN standard didn't use any framework to formalize its definition. Thus, a formalization of BPMN is desired in order to define a method of formal verification of the diagrams, expressed in that notation.

3.4 BPMN Process Diagram's syntax

Definition 9. BPMN Process Diagram is a graph $G := (N, F)$, where:

- $N := A \cup E \cup G$,
 - $A := A_r \cup A_s \cup A_t$
 - $G := G_X \cup G_P$,
 - $E := E_s \cup E_e \cup E_i$,
 - $E_i := E_c \cup E_t$,
 - N, A, G, E are all finite sets
- $F := F_s \cup F_m \cup F_b$ and:
 - $F \subseteq N \times N$,
 - $F_s \subseteq N \times N$,
 - $F_m \subseteq (A \cup E) \times (A \cup E)$,
 - $F_b \subseteq A \times E_c$,

The following naming convention is used:

- N is the set of *Nodes*,
- A is the set of *Activities*, where:
 - A_r is the set of *Receive Tasks*,
 - A_s is the set of *Send Tasks*,

- A_t is the set of *Tasks*,
- G is the set of *Gateways*, where:
 - G_x is the set of *Exclusive Gateways*,
 - G_p is the set of *Parallel Gateways*,
- E is the set of *Events*, where:
 - E_s is the set of *Start Events*,
 - E_e is the set of *End Events*,
 - E_i is the set of *Intermediate Events*,
 - E_c is the set of *Intermediate Catch Events*,
 - E_t is the set of *Intermediate Throw Events*.
- F is the set of transitions in the graph G , also called *flows*, where:
 - F_s is the set of *Sequence Flows*,
 - F_m is the set of *Message Flows*,
 - F_m is the set of *Boundary Links*.

We will also use the following notation:

- $in(E)$ – the set of all incoming flows of the given element E ,
- $out(E)$ – the set of all outgoing flows of the given element E ,
- $in_{seq}(E)$ – the set of all incoming Sequence Flows of the given element E ,
- $in_{mes}(E)$ – the set of all incoming Message Flows of the given element E ,
- $out_{seq}(E)$ – the set of all outgoing Sequence Flows of the given element E ,
- $out_{mes}(E)$ – the set of all outgoing Message Flows of the given element E ,

For any $f = (a, b) \in F$ we define $source(f) := a$ and $target(f) := b$.

In the proposed syntax, *nodes* correspond to *Flow Objects*. They play role of building blocks of BPMN diagrams. They are divided into three general types: *Activities*, *Events* and *Gateways*[4] which in turn are divided into separate subtypes – more on that will be elaborated in subsection 3.6. Figure 2 shows all major subtypes of *Flow Object* that are in scope of this paper.

Figure 2. Chosen subset of BPMN nodes: a) Exclusive Gateway, b) Parallel Gateway, c) Start Event, d) End Event, e) Intermediate Event, f) Task, g) Send Task, h) Receive Task, i) Task with attached Intermediate Boundary Event

F is a non-symmetrical relation which means that for a given element $(n_1, n_2) \in F$ there is a directed connection from n_1 to n_2 . In addition to *Sequence* and *Message Flows*, which are explicitly defined in the BPMN specification, we introduce the concept of *Boundary Links*. We intend to use them as flows connecting Activities with Intermediate Boundary Events attached to them. Figure 3 presents all types of *flows*.

Figure 3. BPMN flows. a) Sequence Flow, b) Message Flow, c) implicit Boundary Link from the Task T to the Boundary Event \mathcal{E}

Each maximal connected component of the underlying undirected graph of $G' := (N, F_s \cup F_b)$ is called a *BPMN Pool*. We omit here intentionally *BPMN Lanes* as the authors of the notation left its meaning to the modeler which is ambiguous[7].

Intermediate Events incident to *Boundary Links* are called *Intermediate Interrupting Boundary Events*.

There are additional syntactical constraints that the graph (N, F) must fulfil:

1. each *Message Flow* must connect elements from two different *Pools*,
2. *Sequence Flows* cannot have as source and target the same node,
3. each *Send Task* must have exactly one outgoing message flow m ; the given *Send Task* has only one incident *Message Flow*,
4. each *Receive Task* must have exactly one incoming message flow m ; the given *Receive Task* has only one incident *Message Flow*,
5. *Start Events* must not have incoming sequence flows,
6. *End Events* must not have outgoing sequence flows,
7. *Intermediate Events* must have at least one incoming and at least one outgoing *Sequence Flow*,
8. *Intermediate Interrupting Boundary Events* must have exactly one incoming flow; the only incoming flow must be a *Boundary Link*.

3.5 BPMN Process Diagram's semantics

In this subsection, a descriptive definition of BPMN semantics is presented. Although mathematical notation is not used extensively, the proposed definition of semantics is as strict as possible. In general, the proposed BPMN semantics is based on the labeled transition system, called *state space*. We introduce gradually all concepts that lead to definition of *state space*, which is proposed in the end of this subsection.

While the general structure of a diagram – its nodes and flows – constitute the static characteristics of a diagram, the concept of *tokens* and their interactions with nodes are introduced to describe the semantics of BPMN[4]. A *token* is a theoretical concept that is responsible for the dynamic behavior of a designed BPMN diagram. In contrast to [4], we model BPMN messages using tokens too, which simplifies semantics of Message Flows.

Definition 10. *State* is a pair $S := (D_{flows}, D_{nodes})$ where:

- D_{flows} is a distribution of *tokens* on flows of the given diagram,
- D_{nodes} is a distribution of symbols $\{neutral, activated, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ on the nodes of the given diagram.

The symbol corresponding to the given node is called *internal state of the node*.

Figure 4 presents general lifecycle of BPMN nodes. *Numeric internal states* (1, 2, ..., n) characterize only those nodes that have incident Message Flows. Nodes that are not incident to Message Flows can only change their state from *neutral* to *activated*. Activities with attached Intermediate Boundary Events can be reset to the state *neutral* at any point of its execution (more on that will be elaborated in the following paragraphs). A cycle through all of element’s internal states, ending in the state *neutral*, is called *execution of the BPMN element*.

Changes of nodes’ *internal states* (and thus changes of the diagram’s global state) happen during one of the following transformations: *node activation*, *exchange of a message*, *node completion* and *Boundary Event handling*.

Figure 4. Possible internal states of a BPMN node and its transformations: a) – lifecycle of nodes that are incident to Message Flows, b) – lifecycle of nodes that are not incident to Message Flows, c) – lifecycle of Activities with attached Intermediate

Definition 11. *Node activation* is the situation in which the required number of tokens are put on the incoming Sequence Flows and Boundary Links of a given BPMN element and the node is in the *neutral* state. During *activation* of the BPMN element, the number of tokens from its incoming flows that triggered the activation is consumed (the tokens disappear) and at the same time the node's internal state changes to *activated*.

Activation simulates the moment in the lifecycle of business process when the modelled BPMN element starts to be executed. In general, it is followed either by *exchange of messages*, if the element has incident Message Flows (graph *a*) on Figure 4), by *completion* of the element's execution (graph *b*) on Figure 4) or additionally, by *Boundary Event handling* (graph *c*) on Figure 4) if the given node is an Activity with a Boundary Event attached to it.

Each BPMN element follows either of the two activation patterns:

- *XOR activation pattern*,
- *AND activation pattern*.

If a BPMN element follows the *XOR activation pattern*, it means that a token put on **any** of its incoming Sequence Flows or Boundary Links will activate the element. In case the BPMN element follows the *AND activation pattern* it means that a token must be put on **each** of its incoming Sequence Flows in order to activate it. Figure 5 presents the dynamics of each of the *activation patterns*. Left side of each of the arrows presents preconditions, while the right side presents postconditions.

Figure 5. Activation patterns of BPMN elements: a) – XOR activation pattern on the example of Exclusive Gateway, b) – AND activation pattern on the example of Parallel Gateway. Green dots symbolize tokens on the incoming Sequence Flows.

Definition 12. *Exchange of messages* is sequential generation of tokens on the outgoing Message Flows and consumption of tokens from the incoming Message Flows. Message Flows incident to the element are processed one at a time, in a left-to-right and then upper-to-lower manner. If the given incoming Message Flow does not contain a token, the message exchange will be blocked until such a token appears on it.

Figure 6. Sequential exchange of messages on the example of an activated Task.

Figure 6 shows generation/consumption of tokens and changes of internal states of a Task that has incident Message Flows. After *activation*, the Task is waiting for a token to be put on the upper left Message Flow. The token is consumed as soon as it appears there and the internal state of the Task changes to *1*. Afterwards, a token is generated on lower left Message Flow and the Task's *internal state* changes to *2*. The following steps include waiting to consume a token from the upper right Message Flow, change of the state to *3*, generation of a token on the lower right outgoing Message Flow and change of the state to *4*. The last state marks the end of exchange of messages and enables *completion* of the Task's execution. In short, each *numeric internal state* (*1, 2, ...*) denotes how many Message Flows have already been processed by a given Activity.

Definition 13. *Nodes completion* is generation of the node-specific number of tokens on the outgoing Sequence Flows, given that the node has been *activated* and all messages have been exchanged. At the same time, the state of the node changes to *neutral*. *Nodes completion* marks the end of execution of a given BPMN element.

Analogously to *nodes activation*, each BPMN element follows either of the two *completion patterns*:

- *XOR completion pattern*,
- *AND completion pattern*.

If a BPMN element follows the *XOR completion pattern*, it means that a token will be generated non-deterministically on **exactly one** of its outgoing Sequence Flows. In case the BPMN element follows the *AND activation pattern* it means that a token will be generated on **each** of its outgoing Sequence Flows. Figure 7 presents the dynamics of each of the *completion patterns*.

Figure 7. Completion patterns of BPMN elements: a) – XOR completion pattern on the example of Exclusive Gateway, b) – AND completion pattern on the example of Parallel Gateway.

Other remarks, concerning *activation* and *completion* of nodes include cases, when a given node:

1. does not have incoming Sequence Flows,
2. does not have outgoing Sequence Flows,
3. both of the above.

If a node does not have incoming Sequence Flows, then it means that it will not be activated by incoming tokens. This includes for example all Start Events and Receive Tasks and any other elements, that don't have incoming Sequence Flows. The concept of *initial state*, introduced in the following paragraphs, resolves the issue of activation of such nodes.

On the other hand, if a node does not have outgoing Sequence Flows, then it means that its completion will not generate any tokens – it will only change the element's internal state to *neutral*. This includes all End Events, Send Tasks and all other elements without outgoing Sequence Flows. In other words, such nodes play the role of *sinks for tokens*, in that their completion lowers the total number of tokens on the diagram.

In case a node does not have any incoming or outgoing Sequence Flows, they will neither ever be activated by a token nor will they generate tokens during its completion. It is still possible for such elements to have incident Message Flows. Because such nodes are activated in the *initial state* (see below), they can still generate tokens during exchange of messages.

Table 1 sums up activation and completion characteristics of each of BPMN element's type. Please note that all Events and Activities follow *XOR activation pattern* and *AND completion pattern*, whereas Gateways differ between Parallel Gateways and Exclusive Gateways. The former follow *AND activation pattern* and *AND completion pattern*, while the latter follow *XOR activation pattern* and *XOR completion pattern*.

Table 1. Summary of activation and execution characteristics of BPMN nodes.

BPMN node	Activation	Completion
Parallel Gateway	AND	AND
Activity	XOR	AND
Event	XOR	AND
Exclusive Gateway	XOR	XOR

An exception to Table 1 are *Activities with Boundary Events*.

Definition 14. *Boundary Event handling* is the ability of Activities with Boundary Events attached to them to change their state to *neutral* at any point of their execution and, at the same time, to generate a token on one of their outgoing Boundary Links.

Boundary Event handling models general *exception handling*. An example of Boundary Event handling is shown on Figure 8. After consumption of the token from the lower Message Flow the state of the Activity is *I*. The Activity should generate a token on the outgoing Message Flow in the *happy path* of its execution, but a Boundary Event occurs. The state of the Activity is set to *neutral* and a token is generated on the Boundary Link. Consequently, the Boundary Event can be activated. Activity doesn't generate tokens anymore in this execution. Occurrence of the Boundary Event might happen in any of the states: *activated*, *I*.

Figure 8. Boundary Event handling. A token on the Boundary Event symbolizes situation, in which a token is put on the Boundary Link between the Activity and the Boundary Event.

Additionally, it is assumed that BPMN uses interleaving semantics – that is, if there are many transformations that are enabled on the diagram, we pick exactly one of them in a non-deterministic manner to be executed. We could argue here, that choosing other semantics is also possible. As was shown in [22], every coincidence-based system can be transformed to interleaved system, possibly by adding some new states.

The concepts of *reachability*, *initial state*, *reachable states*, and *state space* are introduced to complement semantics of BPMN.

Definition 15. Consider state *A*. We say that state *B* is *reachable* from *A* iff. there exists a transformation (*nodes activation*, *exchange of messages*, *nodes completion*, *Boundary Event handling*) that leads from *A* to *B*. We denote this fact with $(A, B) \in R$, where *R* is a binary relationship defined on all possible states of the diagram.

Definition 16. *Initial state* is the state $S_0 = (D_{flows}, D_{nodes})$ where:

- $D_{flows}(f) = 0$ for all flows,
- $D_{nodes}(n) = \begin{cases} \text{activated, } |in_{seq}(n)| = 0 \text{ and } n \text{ is not a Boundary Event} \\ \text{neutral, } n \text{ has incoming Sequence Flows} \end{cases}$

The initial state of the diagram is implied by its structure. Namely, all nodes with no incoming Sequence Flows that are not Boundary Event are initially in the *activated* state.

Definition 17. Consider state A . *Reachable states* are all states that can be reached from A by executing a sequence of transformations (*nodes activation, exchange of messages, nodes completion, Boundary Event handling*). The set of all states reachable from the state A is denoted with $\mathcal{R}(A)$.

Definition 18. *State space* of the BPMN diagram G is the graph $S := (\mathcal{R}(S_0), R)$.

To sum up, vertices of *states space* are states of the given BPMN diagram, that are reachable from its initial marking. Edges of the *state space* are transformations, that lead from one state to another.

3.6 Informal description of BPMN elements

3.6.1 Pools

Pools are containers for other BPMN elements[4]. They are drawn as long rectangles with perpendicular labels with their name. They can be oriented either vertically or horizontally, but BPMN guidelines recommend to consequently follow one convention of *Pools*' orientation. If there is no *Pool* explicitly given on the diagram, then it is assumed that every element on the diagram is contained within a common implicit *Pool*. Figure 9 shows an example of a BPMN Pool, that represents a company.

Pools represent independent participants of a business process. They usually model entities such as companies, clients, manufacturers etc.

Figure 9. Example of a BPMN Pool.

3.6.2 Activities

Activities are executable elements that represent points in a process in which work is performed[4]. They model that certain workload must be done – for example an invoice must be issued, a service must be executed etc. They are drawn as rounded rectangles with solid black line and optionally a symbol of their subtype in upper left corner.

Figure 10. BPMN Activities: a) Task, b) Send Task, c) Receive Task.

Figure 10 shows all major types of Activities that this paper addresses – a) Task, b) Receive Task, c) Send Task. The differences between them are defined in the proposed syntax of BPMN. *Tasks* can have any number of incoming and outgoing Sequence and Message Flows, *Send Tasks* must have exactly one outgoing Message Flow, while *Receive Tasks* must have exactly one incoming Message Flow.

3.6.3 Events

Events are elements that affect the sequence or timing of Activities[4]. In general, they model the entrance and terminating points of processes or things that are relevant to processes but happen independently of it or asynchronously within its context. They do not involve any work to be completed – they only model that something *happens*.

Events are drawn as circles with their subtype symbol in the middle. There are three types of Events: *Start Events*, *Intermediate Events* and *End Events*. *Event's* type is distinguished by border thickness: thin border is reserved for Start Events, double thin border for Intermediate Events and thick border for End Events.

Figure 11. Generic Events: a) Start Event, b) Intermediate Event, c) End Event.

3.6.3.1 Start Events

Start Events model entrant point of the process. They are drawn with a thin line. Figure 12 presents all subtypes of Start Events that are in scope of this paper, including: a) Start Event, b) Message Start Event, c) Timer Start Event, d) Conditional Start Event, e) Signal Start Event. Semantics of each of the subtype of Start Event is the same. Subtypes of Start Event model different triggers that can cause execution of the process.

Figure 12. BPMN Start Events. a) Start Event, b) Message Start Event, c) Timer Start Event, d) Conditional Start Event, e) Signal Start Event.

3.6.3.2 Intermediate Events

Intermediate Events model things that can happen between start and end of a process. They are drawn with a double thin line with their subtype symbol in the middle. Intermediate Events can be divided into two groups. Figure 13 presents all subtypes of Intermediate Events that are in scope of this paper, including: a) Intermediate Message Catch Event, b) Intermediate Signal Catch Event, c) Intermediate Timer Catch Event, d) Intermediate Conditional Catch Event, e) Intermediate Error Catch Event, f) Intermediate Message Throw Event, g) Intermediate Signal Throw Event. The upper row consists of Intermediate Catch Events, while the lower consists of Intermediate Throw Events. The purpose of the former is to model triggers of different nodes. The purpose of the latter is to model result of execution.

Figure 13. BPMN Intermediate Events: a) Intermediate Message Catch Event, b) Intermediate Signal Catch Event, c) Intermediate Timer Catch Event, d) Intermediate Conditional Catch Event, e) Intermediate Error Catch Event, f) Intermediate Message Throw Event, g) Intermediate Signal Throw Event.

3.6.3.3 End Events

End Events indicate where a process will end. They are drawn with a single, thick line and a symbol of result inside of it. Figure 14 shows all End Events that are in scope of this paper, including a) End Event, b) Message End Event, c) Signal End Event. Subtypes of End Events are intended to model different types of results of execution of the given process.

Figure 14. BPMN End Events: a) End Event, b) Message End Event, c) Signal End Event.

3.6.4 Gateways

Figure 15. BPMN Gateways: a) Exclusive Gateway, b) Parallel Gateway.

Gateways are elements that are responsible for branching, forking and joining of processes execution. In other words, they control splitting and merging of tokens. Their execution happens instantly and are assumed to have no impact on the overall cost of the process. They are drawn as flipped squares with subtype symbol in the middle.

Figure 15 shows Gateways addressed in this paper, including a) Exclusive Gateway, b) Parallel Gateway. Exclusive Gateways consume a token from one of its incoming Sequence Flows and generate exactly one new token on one of its outgoing Sequence Flows. Parallel Gateways in turn, consume a token from all of its incoming Sequence Flows, given that each of them contains a one. Afterwards, a new token is generated per each of its outgoing Sequence Flows.

3.7 Discussion on the remaining BPMN elements

Because the standard BPMN notation contains about 70 elements[4] and only a subset of them is considered in this thesis, the remaining elements are briefly discussed in this subsection. BPMN elements that are elaborated below were subject to the author research. For each of them, possible extensions to the proposed BPMN syntax and semantics are sketched or imposed problems with their formalization are discussed. Remaining BPMN elements that are not presented below are fully out of scope of this thesis.

Figure 16. Activities that are not considered in this thesis: a) Sub-processes, b) Call Activity.

To begin with, *Sub-processes* (left graph on Figure 16) are Activities which contain other Flow Objects within their boundaries. Their purpose is to embed a group of other Activities. Whenever a token is passed to a *Sub-process*, its internal logic is executed. When it finishes, tokens are generated on its outgoing flows.

To cover *Sub-processes*, the proposed BPMN semantics could be extended in the following way: whenever a token is put on *Sub-processes* incoming Sequence Flow, all its Start Events get activated; whenever an End Event of a *Sub-process* is completed, tokens are generated on all the Sequence Flows coming out of the *Sub-process*.

Call Activities (right graph on Figure 16) are in turn Activities, which spawn execution of a different BPMN process. In their case, the proposed BPMN semantics could be extended by adding a new type of implicit edges to the BPMN graph between *Call Activities* and all Start Events of the called processes, similar to Boundary Links introduced in the proposed syntax of BPMN. Whenever a *Call Activity* executes, it would generate tokens on those edges, which would in turn cause activation of the processes' Start Events.

Other types of BPMN Activities – *User Tasks*, *Manual Tasks*, *Script Tasks*, *Business Rule Tasks*, *Service Tasks* can be treated like normal *Tasks*, ie. they have the same semantics.

Compensation Events and *Cancel Events* are both Boundary Events and are used in context of a *Transaction Sub-Process*[23] (see Figure 17). They are used together to revoke all changes that a given *Transaction Sub-Process* caused. Firing of a *Cancel Event* causes activation of all *Compensation Events* enclosed by the *Transaction Sub-process*. Therefore, introducing a new type of edges, similar to the one proposed for *Call Activities*, could enable formalization of those events. Such edges would connect a *Cancel Event* with its corresponding *Compensation Events*. Tokens generated on them after execution of the *Cancel Event* would activate *Compensation Events*.

Figure 17. Usage of Cancel and Compensation Events: a) Compensation Event, b) Cancel Event, c) Transaction Sub-Process with Cancel Event and an Activity with attached Compensation Event.

Link Events are intended to be used as “go-to” instructions[24]. Therefore, a pair of Link Intermediate Throw Event and Link Intermediate Catch Event can be replaced by a Sequence Flow. Figure 18. shows Link Intermediate Throw Event (upper row) and a paired Link Intermediate Catch Event (lower row).

Figure 18. Link Events.

Inclusive Gateways generate tokens on any subset of its outgoing Sequence Flows. Such a semantics is referred to as *OR semantics* in the academic world and it imposes a well-known problem concerning *joins* [25]. Namely, it is impossible to decide at the *OR-join* which incoming flows must contain a token in order to fire the gateway without explicit information which tokens must be merged.

The authors of [25] proposes to use only *well-structured* constructs of *OR-splits* and *joins*, that is, not to use *OR-splits* without an accompanying *OR-join* and additionally to use the concept of *false tokens passing* to mark which flows were not chosen during execution of *OR-split*. Such a solution limits the syntax of *Inclusive Gateways* to bracket structures but enables unambiguous semantics for them. Figure 19 shows a pair of *well-structured Inclusive Gateways*. The book [7] proposes a different approach. It introduces the concept of *upstream tokens*, that is, analysis of tokens that can reach a given Inclusive Gateway. Incoming Sequence Flows that already contain tokens are analyzed differently than those that are not yet enabled.

In general, the possible ways in which *Inclusive Gateways* can be formalized either limit the expressiveness of their usage or are complicated.

Figure 19. Well-structured Inclusive Gateways.

Event-based Gateways are gateways that generate tokens on the outgoing Sequence Flows depending on occurrences of events bound to them. Figure 20 shows an *Event-based Gateway* with a Timer Event, Conditional Event and Message Catch Event. Depending on which of the three events occurs faster, the gateway will generate a token on the outgoing Sequence Flow corresponding to it.

According to OMG[4], *Event-based Gateway*'s behavior is defined by Intermediate Events connected to it. Those events are called *gateways configuration* and play key role in *Event-based Gateways* semantics. It is possible to formalize its execution by introducing new transformations that would simulate the race condition on that gateway.

Figure 20. Event-based Gateway.

4 Translation of BPMN into IMDS

4.1 Normalization

In order to verify a given BPMN graph in Integrated Model of Distributed Systems a method of BPMN translation into IMDS is proposed by the author of this thesis. It consists of two steps:

1. BPMN graph normalization,
2. translation of the normalized BPMN graph into IMDS.

Definition 19. BPMN graph normalization is the process of:

- appending Start Events to all elements e which are not Events and for which $|in_{seq}(e)| = 0$,
- appending End Events to all elements e for which are not Events and for which $|out_{seq}(e)| = 0$,
- refactoring all BPMN elements e that are not Exclusive Gateways and Parallel Gateways into semantically equivalent constructs in which $|out_{seq}(e)| = 1$ and $|in_{seq}(e)| = 1$.

The proposed way of normalization simplifies the logic of translation from BPMN to IMDS. The first two rules follow directly from the BPMN specification of nodes that do not have incoming or outgoing Sequence Flows[4]. The third rule guarantees, that elements which follow mixed *XOR activation* and *AND completion* semantics are transformed into equivalent groups of elements, which in turn follow either *XOR activation* and *XOR completion semantics* or *AND activation* and *AND completion semantics*. We consider any node that follows *AND completion semantics* and has single outgoing Sequence Flow to also follow *XOR completion pattern*. It is not contradictory to the definition of *completion semantics* proposed for BPMN in the particular case if there is only one outgoing Sequence Flow.

Table 2 shows the rules of BPMN elements normalization. The first column contains a short description, the second contains graphical representation and the third shows node normalization. A given BPMN element may have incident Message Flows. In this case, all Message Flows remain as-is on the normalized graph.

Table 2. Normalization rules of BPMN elements

Name	BPMN element	Normalized BPMN element
Start Events		
End Events		

Intermediate Events		
Activities		
Nodes with no incoming sequence flow		
Nodes with no outgoing sequence flow		

Normalized graph simulates the original graph. All paths possible in the original graph are also possible in the normalized graph, because normalization does not change reachability of each of the original nodes.

4.2 Translation of normalized graph into IMDS

In this subsection, translation of a *normalized BPMN graph* into IMDS is described. We use terms *servers*, *agents*, *actions*, *states* and *services* to refer to elements of the resulting IMDS model. The resulting model is formally the tuple $(S, A, M_{init}, R_{init}, F)$, where S is the set of *servers*, A is the set *agents*, M_{init} is the set of initial states of *servers*, R_{init} is the set of *initial messages* for *agents*, and F is the set of *actions*.

The proposed BPMN-to-IMDS translation tries to mimic the dynamic behavior of internal states of BPMN elements (Figure 21). In general, BPMN tokens are mapped into messages of IMDS agents. Flows are mapped into IMDS services. Just like tokens traverse the BPMN diagram, messages are exchanged between IMDS servers, that are created during translation. Node activation, execution of Message Flows, node completion and Boundary Event handling are all mimicked by IMDS actions. The act of consumption of a token from an incoming flow of a node and generation of another one on one of its outgoing flows is modeled by execution of an IMDS action.

Figure 21. Dynamics of BPMN elements.

Elements of a BPMN diagram can be divided into nine groups with respect to the way that they are mapped into IMDS:

1. Pools,
2. Sequence Flows,
3. Message Flows,
4. Start Events that do not have incident Message Flows,
5. End Events that do not have incident Message Flows,
6. nodes that follow *XOR activation pattern* and *XOR completion pattern* that do not have incident Message Flows,
7. Boundary Events,
8. nodes that follow *AND activation pattern* and *AND execution pattern* that do not have incident Message Flows,
9. nodes that have incident Message Flows.

Rules of translation for each of the above groups are presented on Table 3. A given Pool \mathcal{S} is translated into server $pool(\mathcal{S})$, also called *Pool server*, with a single state defined on it: *ready* and a set of IMDS agents bound to it, called $agents(\mathcal{S})$. Sequence Flows constitute services of a given server $pool(\mathcal{S})$. Each Message Flow m constitutes a new set of agents, called $agents(m)$ and services on the *AND servers* of $source(m)$ and $target(m)$ – more on *AND servers* will be elaborated in the following subsection. Groups 4., 5. and 6. And 7. are translated to actions on their corresponding Pool \mathcal{S} and $agents(\mathcal{S})$. Rules 8. and 9. transform the given node n that is contained within a Pool \mathcal{S} using $createAND(...)$ function into a tuple consisting of:

- a new server $and(n, \mathcal{S})$, also called *AND server*,
- a set of actions defined on the *AND server*,
- a set of actions defined on the corresponding Pool \mathcal{S} ,
- new agents in $agents(\mathcal{S})$,
- initial messages for the new agents.

Elements of this tuple form additional components of the translated IMDS model. Due to its complexity, the function $createAND(n, \mathcal{P})$ is described in a separate subsection.

Because IMDS agents can't be created dynamically, they must be preallocated during translation of BPMN into IMDS. More on this will be elaborated in the subsection about limitations of the proposed translation. For now, let's introduce the number parameter K to define how many agents are created on each Message Flow and in the $createAND(n, \mathcal{P}, K)$ function.

Table 3. Rules of translation of BPMN into IMDS. The translation is parameterized using the numeric constant K . The resulting IMDS systems is denoted $(S, A, M_{init}, R_{init}, F)$.

<p>Pool \mathcal{S} (group 1.)</p>	<p>set of agents $agent(\mathcal{S}) \subseteq A$, server $pool(\mathcal{S}) = (\mathcal{S}, V_{\mathcal{S}}, Q_{\mathcal{S}}) \in \mathcal{S}$ $V_{\mathcal{S}} = \{ready\}$ initial server state $(pool(\mathcal{S}), ready) \in M_{init}$</p>
<p>Sequence Flow f within Pool \mathcal{S} (group 2.)</p>	<p>service $f \in Q_{\mathcal{S}}$</p>
<p>Message Flow f between Task A in Pool X and Task B in Pool Y (group 3.)</p>	<p>service $f \in Q_{and(A)}$, service $f \in Q_{and(B)}$, set $agents(f) = \{agent_f^j \mid j \in \{1, \dots, K\}\} \subseteq A$ initial messages for agents from $agents(f)$: $M_f = \{m_f^j \mid (agent_f^j, and(A), f) \wedge j \in \{1, \dots, K\}\} \subseteq R_{init}$</p>
<p>Start Event \mathcal{E} in Pool \mathcal{S} (group 4.)</p>	<p>agent $a_f \in agents(\mathcal{S})$, initial message $(a_f, pool(\mathcal{S}), f) \in R_{init}$</p>
<p>End Event \mathcal{E} in Pool \mathcal{S} (group 5.)</p>	<p>action $\{(agents(\mathcal{S}), pool(\mathcal{S}), f), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\} \rightarrow$ $\{(agents(\mathcal{S}), -, -), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\} \in F$</p>
<p>Node in Pool \mathcal{S} following <i>XOR activation</i> and <i>XOR execution semantics</i> (group 6.)</p>	<p>set of actions: $\{(agents(\mathcal{S}), pool(\mathcal{S}), in_i), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\} \rightarrow$ $\{(agents(\mathcal{S}), pool(\mathcal{S}), out_j), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\} \subseteq F$ $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$</p>

<p>Interrupting Intermediate Boundary Event \mathcal{E} bound to Task \mathcal{T} in Pool \mathcal{S} (group 7.)</p>	<p>2 actions on swimlane s:</p> $\{(agents(\mathcal{S}), pool(\mathcal{S}), in), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\} \rightarrow \{(agents(\mathcal{S}), pool(\mathcal{S}), f), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\},$ $\{(agents(\mathcal{S}), pool(\mathcal{S}), in), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\} \rightarrow \{(agents(\mathcal{S}), pool(\mathcal{S}), out), (pool(\mathcal{S}), ready)\} \subseteq F$
<p>Node n contained within Pool \mathcal{S}, n is from group 8. or 9.</p>	<p>tuple</p> $(andServer, andActions, poolActions, agents, initialMessages)$ <p>= $createAND(n, \mathcal{S}, K)$, where:</p> $andServer \in S,$ $andActions \subseteq F,$ $poolActions \subseteq F,$ $agents \subseteq A,$ $initialMessages \subseteq R_{init},$ <p>additionally the initial state for the new <i>AND server</i>:</p> $(andServer, 0) \in M_{init}$

4.3 Creation of *AND servers*

AND servers are IMDS servers that are generated during translation of BPMN elements from groups 8. and 9.

The concept of *AND servers* is introduced in order to:

- mimic the merging and splitting behavior of *AND execution* and *AND activation patterns*, that is, atomic consumption and generation of multiple tokens,
- mimic consumption and generation of tokens on Message Flows during execution of a BPMN node.

Those two BPMN constructs share the same translation into IMDS for practical reasons.

Consider a BPMN element n with $in_{seq}(n) = k$ and $out_{seq}(n) = l$ that follows *AND activation* and *AND execution patterns*. That means, that the node activation will consume atomically k tokens from its incoming Sequence Flows and node completion will generate atomically l tokens on its outgoing Sequence Flows. Such a semantics is not possible in IMDS because execution of an action always consumes exactly one message and generates another one for a given IMDS agent. Thus, the author proposes

to mimic atomic generation (or consumption) of tokens on x Sequence Flows that are adjacent to the node n with sequential execution of x IMDS actions. The IMDS translation of the node n must keep track of how many IMDS actions have already been executed. As a translation of the node n , the author proposes to introduce a new server, called *AND server* with states from the set $\{0, 1, \dots, k + l - 1\}$ and actions defined on it that simulate the merging and splitting behavior. If additionally the node n has incident Message Flows, then they are also translated into IMDS actions, similar to those actions that correspond to Sequence Flows. The initial state of every *AND server* is set initially to 0 .

Definition 20. Consider a node n in Pool \mathcal{P} with a set of incident flows $F := \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N\}$. Let the indexes of elements of F order flows in the following manner: first all incoming Sequence Flows in an arbitrary order, next all Message Flows ordered in the left-to-right and then upper-to-lower manner on the graph, followed by all outgoing Sequence Flows in arbitrary order. Let $|in_{mes}(n)| + |out_{mes}(n)| = x$. Let $in_{seq}(n) = y$. Let k be a numeric parameter. Function *create-AND*(n, \mathcal{P}, k) produces the following tuple: (*and*(n), *andActions*, *poolActions*, *agents*, *initialMessages*), where:

- *and*(n) is the new server $\mathcal{S} := (n, V, Q)$, for which:
 - n is the name of the server, equal to the name of the BPMN node,
 - $V := \{0, 1, 2, \dots, (N - 1)\}$ is the set of server states,
 - $Q := F$ is the set of server services.
- *andActions* is the set of actions defined by the result of the procedure *andActions*(n, \mathcal{P}),
- *poolActions* is the set of actions defined by:

$$poolActions = \left\{ action_{f_i} \left| \begin{array}{l} action_{f_i} = ((agents(\mathcal{P}), pool(\mathcal{P}), f_i), (pool(\mathcal{P}), ready)) \\ \rightarrow ((agents(\mathcal{P}), and(n), f_i), (pool(\mathcal{P}), ready)) \\ \wedge f_i \in F \\ \wedge i \leq y \end{array} \right. \right\}$$

- *agents* is the set of new elements of *agents*(\mathcal{P}):

$$agents = \left\{ agent_{f_i}^j \left| \begin{array}{l} f_i \in \{f_p, f_{p+1}, \dots, f_N\} \\ \wedge f_p \in F \\ \wedge 2y + x < p \leq N \\ \wedge j \in \{1, \dots, k\} \end{array} \right. \right\}$$

- *initialMessages* is the set of initial messages for elements of *agents*:

$$messages = \left\{ message_i^j \left| \begin{array}{l} message_i^j = (agent_{f_i}^j, and(source(fi), f_i)) \\ \wedge agent_{f_i}^j \in agents \end{array} \right. \right\}.$$

The listing of the procedure *andActions* is presented below:

```

1  procedure andActions
2  input:
3    n: BPMN node, N - incident flows, m - incident Message Flows;
4    P: BPMN pool that contains n
5  variables:
6    actions := ∅
7    a := null
8  begin:
9    subprocedure create // concise creation of IMDS actions
10   input:
11     A: set of IMDS agents,
12     q: initial service,
13     p: continuation service,
14     x: initial state,
15     y: continuation state,
16     s: initial server,
17     r: continuation server
18   begin:
19     return IMDS action ((A, s, q), (s, x) → ((A, r, p), (s, y))
20   end
21   for i := 1 to N
22     if fi is an incoming Sequence Flow and i + m ≤ n:
23       a := create(agents(P), fi, fi, i-1, i, and(n), and(n))
24     if fi is an incoming Sequence Flow and i + m > n
25       a := create(agents(P), fi, -, i-1, i, and(n), -)
26     if fi is an incoming Message Flow
27       a := create(agents(fi), fi, -, i-1, i, and(n), -)
28     if fi is an outgoing Message Flow
29       a := create(agents(fi), fi, fi, i-1, i, and(n), and(target(fi)))
30     if fi is an outgoing Sequence Flow
31       a := create(agents(P), fi, fi, i-1, i mod N, and(n), pool(P))
32     add a into actions
33   return actions
34 end

```

Let's discuss how *createAND(n, P, k)* works. Consider a node *n* in a Pool *P* that is translated into IMDS using that function. The resulting *AND server* is responsible for simulation of *n* as far as joining tokens, exchange of messages and forking tokens are concerned. To do so, services and actions corresponding to all its incident flows are defined in such a way, that execution of action corresponding to any of the flows raises up the state of the server. Figure 22 shows the execution dynamics of the resulting *and(n) server*. Circles represent its states and edges represent execution of actions generated by *andActions(n, P)*. Figure 22 clearly reminds execution dynamics of a BPMN element from Figure 21. They both are characterized by cyclic structure, with the only difference being that *activation* and *completion* from Figure 21 are mimicked by execution of multiple IMDS services.

Figure 22: State changes on $and(n)$ server after execution of services. N is the number of incident flows.

The set of *pool actions* ($poolActions$) is used to call services on the AND server from the enclosing Pool's IMDS server. The set of *andActions* plays symmetrical role in that its elements send messages from the AND server back to the Pool server.

Let's discuss how the set *andActions* is created. Each incoming Sequence Flow f_i of the node is paired with an outgoing Sequence Flow f_o , given that there are enough outgoing Sequence Flows to create unique pairs. The idea is to translate all such pairs of form (f_i, f_o) into IMDS actions that execute service f_i and next call f_o (lines 22-23 of the procedure). Green color on Figure 23 shows an example of a pairing of an incoming to an outgoing Sequence Flow; f_1 is bound to f_3 which means that execution of f_1 on the AND server by an agent a will be followed by calling service f_3 by a . Because there are only one outgoing Sequence Flow, f_2 will not be bound. All unbound incoming Sequence Flows constitute on the AND server terminating actions (lines 24-25 of the procedure). In the case of Figure 23 it means that execution of f_2 will terminate the agent that called it.

Figure 23. Creation of a pair *incoming Sequence Flow - outgoing Sequence Flow*.

Next, all incoming Message Flows are translated into actions that raise the servers state by one and terminate agents bound to the given Message Flow. All outgoing Message Flows m are translated into actions that raise the servers state by one and call the service m on $and(target(m))$ – that is, on the server corresponding to the node that is the target of the flow (lines 26-29 of the procedure). Please note, that agents corresponding to the given Message Flow are preallocated according to Table 3.

In the end of $andAction(n, \mathcal{P})$ procedure, the outgoing Sequence Flows are translated into actions that raise the servers state by one and send the agents back to the Pool server (lines 30-31). The last step

sets the AND server state to 0 instead of raising it up by 1 in order to set the server state to the initial value again (note the $\text{mod } N$ operation in the definition of *continuation state*).

Final note on the function $\text{createAND}(n, \mathcal{P}, k)$ concerns creation of the set *agents*. It aims to resolve the problem when the node has more outgoing than incoming Sequence Flows. Outgoing Sequence Flows which do not have a binding constitute preallocated agents. For each of them, k agents are created with initial messages calling their corresponding service.

4.4 Limitations of the proposed translation

The proposed translation method has some major issues which should be taken into account. The first is that IMDS agents can't be created dynamically. In order to simulate dynamic creation of tokens, the concept of *preallocation of agents* is introduced. Let's discuss what impact does this have on the BPMN-to-IMDS translation.

To begin with, the translation method cannot work for diagrams whose execution may generate infinitely many tokens, such as the example on Figure 24. On this example, completion of the Parallel Gateway will cause its activation again. Infinitely many tokens can be generated on the Sequence Flow f . We refer to such diagrams as *unbounded*.

Figure 24. Example of an *unbounded* BPMN diagram.

Preallocation of agents creates *a priori* more IMDS agents than it could be needed. The total number of agents that exist in the resulting IMDS system is defined by the translation parameter K . Theoretically, the K parameter could also be infinitely big, but this would disable static creation of state space of the resulting IMDS model. It makes the proposed translation method useless for *unbounded* diagrams. This problem stems from the IMDS nature and cannot be handled by any improvement of the translation method.

Moreover, incorrect choosing of the K parameterization leads to false behavior of the IMDS system. Consider Figure 25, on which Parallel Gateway G can be executed two times.

Figure 25. Example of a Parallel Gateway that can be executed two times.

If the translation method is parametrized using $K = 1$, then only a single agent will be created for the Sequence Flow f. First execution of the Parallel Gateway G is correctly simulated by the translated IMDS model. The problem arises when the gateway is executed for the second time. In this case, there is no agent whose message can mimic the behavior of the token generated for the second time on the Sequence Flow f. Using parametrization $K = 2$ solves the problem, because there is a second preallocated agent, whose message is simulating the token generated during the second execution of the gateway.

Thus, K has to be chosen carefully, preferably using additional information about how many times each of the BPMN elements can be executed. This can be considered as a major limitation to the proposed translation method, but also stems from the nature of IMDS and cannot be handled in any better way than agents preallocation.

The second major problem with the proposed translation method concerns BPMN elements with non-local semantics, like Inclusive Gateways. They were excluded from the proposed syntax, because the author could not propose a correct execution semantics for such elements. Thus, they are also not considered in the translation method.

A minor issue with the proposed translation concerns Boundary Events. Boundary Events attached to Activities that have incident Message Flows are not fully translated by the proposed translation. To fully cover their semantics, a resetting actions should be added to each of the states $\{activated, 1, 2, \dots\}$ of such an Activity.

5 Examples

5.1 Normalization of BPMN diagrams

Figure 26. An example BPMN diagram to be normalized.

The diagram presented on Figure 26 contains an implicit Pool P, Start Event E, End Event F, Tasks P and Q, Intermediate Event I and five Sequence Flows: f_1 , f_2 , f_3 , f_4 , f_5 . During normalization, it is translated into the diagram shown on the Figure 27.

Figure 27 Normalization of the example BPMN diagram.

Note the following changes on Figure 27 comparing to Figure 26:

- Parallel Gateway G_E and Sequence Flows f_E have been added to the Start Event E,
- Exclusive Gateway G_Q and Sequence Flow f_Q have been added to the Task Q,
- Parallel Gateway G_P and Sequence Flow f_P have been added the Task P,
- Exclusive Gateway G_F and Sequence Flow f_F have been added to the End Event F.

5.2 Translation of BPMN into IMDS

5.2.1 XOR activation and XOR execution pattern

Figure 28. Exclusive Gateway.

The example on Figure 29 contains an implicit Pool P , Start Event E_1 , two End Event E_2 and E_3 , Exclusive Gateway G and three Sequence Flows: s_1, s_2, s_3 .

Let $K = 1$ be the parametrization used in the translation. The translation results in the following IMDS system:

$(S, A, M_{init}, R_{init}, F) := ($

$S := \{(pool(P), \{ready\}, \{s_1, s_2, s_3\})\},$

$A := \{a_{s_1}\},$

$M_{init} := \{(P, ready)\},$

$R_{init} := \{(pool(P), a_{s_1}, s_1)\},$

$F := \{((agents(P), pool(P), s_1), (pool(P), ready)) \rightarrow ((agents(P), pool(P), s_2), (pool(P), ready)),$
 $((agents(P), pool(P), s_1), (pool(P), ready)) \rightarrow ((agents(P), pool(P), s_3), (pool(P), ready)),$
 $((agents(P), pool(P), s_2), (pool(P), ready)) \rightarrow ((agents(P), -, -), (pool(P), ready)),$
 $((agents(P), pool(P), s_3), (pool(P), ready)) \rightarrow ((agents(P), -, -), (pool(P), ready))\})$

Additionally, $agents(P) = \{a_{s_1}\}$.

5.2.2 AND activation and AND execution pattern

Figure 29. Parallel Gateway.

The example on Figure 29 contains an implicit Pool P , Start Event E_1 , two End Events E_2 and E_3 , Parallel Gateway G and three Sequence Flows: s_1, s_2, s_3 .

Let $K = 2$ be the parametrization used in the translation. The translation results in the following IMDS system:

$(S, A, M_{init}, R_{init}, F) := ($

$S := \{(\text{pool}(P), \{\text{ready}\}, \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}), (\text{and}(G), \{0, 1, 2\}, \{s_1, s_2, s_3\})\},$

$A := \{a_{s_1}, a_{s_3}^1, a_{s_3}^2\},$

$M_{init} := \{(P, \text{ready}), (\text{and}(G), 0)\},$

$R_{init} := \{(\text{pool}(P), a_{s_1}, s_1), (\text{and}(G), a_{s_3}^1, s_3), (\text{and}(G), a_{s_3}^2, s_3)\},$

$F := \{((\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_1), (\text{pool}(P), \text{ready})) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_1), (\text{pool}(P), \text{ready}))),$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_1), (\text{and}(G), 0) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_2), (\text{and}(G), 1))),$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_2), (\text{and}(G), 1) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_2), (\text{and}(G), 2))),$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_3), (\text{and}(G), 2) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_3), (\text{and}(G), 0))),$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_2), (\text{pool}(P), \text{ready}) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), -, -), (\text{pool}(P), \text{ready}))),$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_3), (\text{pool}(P), \text{ready}) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), -, -), (\text{pool}(P), \text{ready}))\}$

Additionally, $\text{agents}(P) = \{a_s, a_{s_3}^1, a_{s_3}^2\}$. Note the following:

- agent a_{s_1} corresponds to Sequence Flow s_1 that is adjacent to the Start Event E_1 ,
- Sequence Flow s_3 could not be paired with any incoming Sequence Flow, so the number of agents equal to the parametrization K has been preallocated on it. The preallocated agents are: $a_{s_3}^1$ and $a_{s_3}^2$ and both initially call the service s_3 on $\text{and}(G)$.

Moreover, elements of the tuple $(\text{and}(G), \text{andActions}, \text{poolActions}, \text{agents}, \text{initialMessages})$, created by the function $\text{createAND}(G, P, 2)$ include:

- $\text{and}(G) := (\text{and}(G), \{0, 1, 2\}, \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}),$
- $\text{andActions} := \{$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_1), (\text{and}(G), 0) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_2), (\text{and}(G), 1))),$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_2), (\text{and}(G), 1) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_2), (\text{and}(G), 2))),$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_3), (\text{and}(G), 2) \rightarrow (\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_3), (\text{and}(G), 0)))\}$
- $\text{poolActions} := \{$
 $((\text{agents}(P), \text{pool}(P), s_1), (\text{pool}(P), \text{ready})) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(P), \text{and}(G), s_1), \text{pool}(P), \text{ready}))\}$
- $\text{agents} := \{a_{s_3}^1, a_{s_3}^2\},$
- $\text{initialMessages} := \{(\text{and}(G), a_{s_3}^1, s_3), (\text{and}(G), a_{s_3}^2, s_3)\}$

5.2.3 Communication between Pools

Figure 30. Translation of Message Flows.

Figure 30 presents an example of a BPMN diagram that contains Message Flows. It consists of two Pools: X and Y. Pool X consists in turn of Start Event E, Task P, End Event X and two Sequence Flows: s_1 and s_2 . Pool Y consists of Start Event F, Task Q, End Event Y and two Sequence Flows: s_3 and s_4 . There are two Message Flows on the diagram: m_1 from Task P to Task Q and m_2 from Task Q to Task P.

Let $K = I$ be the parametrization used in the translation. The translation results in the following IMDS system:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (S, A, M_{\text{init}}, R_{\text{init}}, F) &:= (\\
 S &:= \{(\text{pool}(X), \{\text{ready}\}, \{s_1, s_2\}), (\text{pool}(Y), \{\text{ready}\}, \{s_3, s_4\}), (\text{and}(P), \{0, 1, 2, 3\}, \{s_1, s_2, m_1, m_2\}), \\
 &(\text{and}(Q), \{0, 1, 2, 3\}, \{s_3, s_4, m_1, m_2\})\}, \\
 A &:= \{a_{s_1}, a_{s_3}, a_{m_1}, a_{m_2}\}, \\
 M_{\text{init}} &:= \{(\text{pool}(X), \text{ready}), (\text{pool}(Y), \text{ready}), (\text{and}(P), 0), (\text{and}(Q), 0)\}, \\
 R_{\text{init}} &:= \{(\text{pool}(X), a_{s_1}, s_1), (\text{pool}(Y), a_{s_3}, s_3), (\text{and}(P), a_{m_1}, m_1), (\text{and}(Q), a_{m_2}, m_2)\}, \\
 F &:= \{((\text{agents}(X), \text{pool}(X), s_1), (\text{pool}(X), \text{ready})) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(X), \text{and}(P), s_1), (\text{pool}(X), \text{ready})), \\
 &((\text{agents}(X), \text{pool}(X), s_2), (\text{pool}(X), \text{ready})) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(X), -, -), (\text{pool}(X), \text{ready})), \\
 &((\text{agents}(Y), \text{pool}(Y), s_3), (\text{pool}(Y), \text{ready})) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(Y), \text{and}(Q), s_3), (\text{pool}(Y), \text{ready})), \\
 &((\text{agents}(Y), \text{pool}(Y), s_4), (\text{pool}(Y), \text{ready})) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(Y), -, -), (\text{pool}(Y), \text{ready})), \\
 &((\text{agents}(X), \text{and}(P), s_1), (\text{and}(P), 0)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(X), \text{and}(P), s_2), (\text{and}(P), 1)), \\
 &((\text{agents}(m_1), \text{and}(P), m_1), (\text{and}(P), 1)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(m_1), \text{and}(Q), m_1), (\text{and}(P), 2)), \\
 &((\text{agents}(m_2), \text{and}(P), m_2), (\text{and}(P), 2)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(m_2), -, -), (\text{and}(P), 3)), \\
 &((\text{agents}(X), \text{and}(P), s_2), (\text{and}(P), 3)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(X), \text{pool}(X), s_2), (\text{and}(P), 0)), \\
 &((\text{agents}(Y), \text{and}(Q), s_3), (\text{and}(Q), 0)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(Y), \text{and}(Q), s_4), (\text{and}(Q), 1)), \\
 &((\text{agents}(m_1), \text{and}(Q), m_1), (\text{and}(Q), 1)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(m_1), -, -), (\text{and}(Q), 2)), \\
 &((\text{agents}(m_2), \text{and}(Q), m_2), (\text{and}(Q), 2)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(m_2), \text{and}(P), m_2), (\text{and}(Q), 3)), \\
 &((\text{agents}(Y), \text{and}(Q), s_4), (\text{and}(Q), 3)) \rightarrow ((\text{agents}(Y), \text{pool}(Y), s_4), (\text{and}(Q), 0))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Additionally, $\text{agents}(X) = \{ a_{s_1} \}$, $\text{agents}(Y) = \{ a_{s_3} \}$, $\text{agents}(m_1) = \{ a_{m_1} \}$, $\text{agents}(m_2) = \{ a_{m_2} \}$. Note that two AND servers have been created: one for the Task P and a second for the task Q. Sequence Flow s_1 has been paired with Sequence Flow s_2 on $\text{and}(P)$, while s_3 has been paired with Sequence Flow s_4 on $\text{and}(Q)$.

6 Solution

6.1 Requirements

In this section, an application that implements the BPMN-to-IMDS translation is proposed. Functional requirements of such a solution that must be met include:

1. user must be able to load a *.bpmn* file that contains elements from the proposed BPMN syntax (subsection 3.4),
2. the loaded diagram must be visualized,
3. user interface must provide a mechanism to verify the loaded diagram,
4. counterexample in the form of sequence diagram must be displayed for each deadlock,
5. if there is no deadlock on the verified diagram, an appropriate message must be displayed,
6. if there are deadlocks on the verified diagram, there must exist a mechanism to replay each of them separately in a step-by-step simulation,
7. if there are deadlocks on the diagram, a sequence diagram chart must be sketched,
8. user should be able to set the desired parametrization of the BPMN-to-IMDS translation.

Non-functional requirements include:

1. the developed solution must be based on the already existing tool – *Dedan* – which is implemented in C#,
2. interface should support colors on the BPMN diagram in order to mark deadlocks,
3. processing of concurrent verifications should be supported.

Figure 31 presents all the use cases of the solution. They can be divided into four types, depending on the component of the application that they involve.

Figure 31. Use cases of the proposed solution.

Table 4. Description of use cases.

Use case	Preconditions	Steps	Postconditions	Possible errors
<i>Load diagram</i>	none	1. user clicks on “Load diagram” button, 2. user selects a <i>.bpmn</i> file to be loaded	diagram from the selected file is visualized	file is not in the BPMN format
<i>Verify diagram</i>	user loaded a BPMN diagram	user clicks on the “Verify diagram” button	either a list of deadlocks is presented or a message “No deadlocks” is displayed	the diagram contains elements that are not supported by the verification component
<i>Select deadlock</i>	loaded diagram was verified and deadlocks were found	user selects a deadlock from the list	context of the visualization component is set to the chosen deadlock	none
<i>Inspect deadlock</i>	the loaded diagram was verified, deadlocks were found and deadlock to be inspected was set	user clicks on the button “Step forward”, “Step backward”, “First step”, “Last step”	Sequence and Message Flows along the trace of the deadlock are consequently marked blue; when the last step of the deadlock is inspected, the Flows incident to the blocked element that are dead are marked red, those that have been activated are marked green	none
<i>Reset diagram</i>	the loaded diagram was verified and deadlocks were found	user clicks on the button “Reset”	all colors on the diagram are set to black, information about deadlocks disappears	none
<i>Configure verification</i>	none	user sets the desired number of IMDS agents queued on AND-splits in a form	any call to the verification component will use the chosen number as the number of IMDS agents queued on AND-splits	1. input is not a number, 2. input is greater than 3 or non-positive
<i>BPMN-to-IMDS translation</i>	a BPMN diagram was loaded	translation of the BPMN diagram into IMDS is executed	resulting IMDS model is returned	BPMN diagram’s syntax is incorrect
<i>IMDS-to-BPMN translation</i>	the given IMDS model was created by <i>BPMN-to-IMDS translation</i>	mapping of IMDS deadlocks back into the BPMN diagram is executed	a list of deadlocks is returned	the given IMDS model was not created by <i>BPMN-to-IMDS translation</i>

6.2 Proposed solution

Because *Dedan* is implemented using C#, the core logic can extend its already existing data structures by adding functionalities of parsing of a BPMN diagram, mapping it into IMDS, validating the IMDS model using the *TempoRG* verifier and then returning a list of possible deadlocks. This has been implemented in a reusable utility, called *bpmn2imds-core*, which will serve as the engine of translation of BPMN into IMDS.

Additionally, a new functionality to load, verify and inspect BPMN diagrams has been developed in the *Dedan* program. This extension uses the *bpmn2imds-core* utility to load BPMN models and translated them into IMDS. It has primarily debugging purpose, as *Dedan* provides an existing interface to edit and verify models in IMDS.

The last part of the proposed solution is a web application with a user-friendly interface to load and verify BPMN diagrams, called *bpmn2imds-web*. This application is implemented an *Angular*-based application as the user frontend and a *.NET Standard WEB API* as the backend. The backend also uses the *bpmn2imds-core* utility. The *bpmn2imds-web* application implements all the functional and non-functional requirements and the above use cases.

6.3 Implementation

6.3.1 *bpmn2imds-core*

The library *bpmn2imds-core* uses the idea of *graph transformations* to implement the logic of BPMN-to-IMDS translation. In other words, the loaded BPMN diagram is gradually transformed into an intermediate graph structure and in the end – into an IMDS model.

Figure 32 shows the package structure and dependencies of *bpmn2imds-core*. External dependencies include *Dedan*, *BPMN.Sharp*, *QuickGraph* and *Ninject*. The *Dedan* package was designed at the Institute of Computer Science, Warsaw University of Technology. It is used to create data structures to specify models in IMDS, like *servers*, *states*, *services*, *agents* and *actions* and to verify them using *TempoRG* verifier. *BPMN.Sharp* [26] is used to parse BPMN diagrams. It is a C# library by B. Zinchenko to process BPMN diagrams. It comes with an out-of-the-box reader of .bpmn files. Further processing of the given BPMN diagram is achieved using the *QuickGraph*[27] library. *QuickGraph* is a mature, tested graph library used by hundreds of thousands of developers[28]. It provides a wide variety of graph data structures and algorithms. *BidirectionalGraph<V,E>* type will be used as the base class all the graphs that are created during processing of the given BPMN diagram. The *Ninject* library is used as the dependency injection framework.

Figure 32. Package structure and dependencies of *bpmn2imds-core*.

Internal packages of *bpmn2imds-core* include: *Graphs*, *IMDSTypes*, *Deadlocks*, *Setup* and *bpmn2imds*. Package *Graphs* contains definitions of graphs that are transformed during the process of translation. It extends objects from the package *QuickGraph*. Package *IMDSTypes* defines extensions of objects from the package *IMDS*: custom, strongly typed *servers*, *agents* and *actions*. Package *Deadlocks* contains definitions for data structures used to represent deadlocks found on a BPMN diagram. Package *Setup* is responsible for wiring up dependency injection. Package *bpmn2imds* is the main package of the *bpmn2imds-core*. It is responsible for translation of BPMN diagrams into IMDS systems, executing their verification and mapping possible deadlocks back to BPMN.

Figure 33 presents the main class of *bpmn2imds-core*. It is called *BPMN2IMDS* and is contained within the package *bpmn2imds*.

BPMN2IMDS consists of two parts: one responsible for loading BPMN diagrams using *BPMN.Sharp*, called *BPMNParser*, and the second responsible for the actual translation of the BPMN diagram into IMDS, called *Translator*. *BPMN2IMDS* includes a method to set the examined BPMN diagram *SetModel(model)*, a method to load a BPMN diagram from file system *LoadModel(path)*, a method translate the BPMN diagram into an IMDS model called *GetIMDS()* and a method to verify the diagram called *GetDeadlocks()*.

Figure 33: The class diagram of *bpmn2imds-core* generated using Visual Studio

Let's discuss the logic of processing of BPMN diagrams. The UML Activity Diagram of Figure 34 presents the dynamics of that function.

Figure 34. Graph transformations of a BPMN diagram.

The first step, *parsing of a BPMN file*, is executed during a call to *BPMN2IMDS.SetModel(model)* if the *BPMN.Sharp* representation of the diagram has been created prior to the call, or during a call to *BPMN2IMDS.LoadModel(path)* if the diagram is to be loaded from the local file system.

The three following steps – *creation of QuickGraph representation*, *application of normalization* and *application of translation* – are all wrapped in the method *BPMN2IMDS.GetIMDS()*. This method

returns an instance of *Model_S* – a class from the *Dedan* package, which represents IMDS model that can be interpreted by the *TempoRG* verifier.

Creation of *QuickGraph* representation is done by *BPMNParser.GeneratEssentialGraph(model)*, which takes as the argument the loaded instance of the diagram in *BPMN.Sharp* format. The result of its execution is in turn an instance of the class *EssentialGraph*, which extends *QuickGraph*'s *BidirectionalGraph<T,E>*.

The *BPMNParser.GeneratEssentialGraph(model)* method executes the syntax verification of the diagram according with compliance to subsection 3.4. It ensures that the diagram follows the syntactical constraints defined in the proposed BPMN syntax. Errors that can be thrown by that method are presented on Figure 35. They all inherit from the class *GenericValidationException*. They include:

- *IncomingMessageFlowException* – an error if the given element has incoming Message Flow but it should not,
- *OutgoingMessageFlowException* – an error if the given element has outgoing Message Flow but it should not,
- *OutgoingSequenceFlowException* – an error if the given element has outgoing Sequence Flow but it should not,
- *IncomingSequenceFlowException* – an error if the given element has incoming Sequence Flow but it should not,
- *UnsupportedBPMNElementTypeException* – an error if the type of the given element is not supported by *bpmn2imds-core*.

Figure 35. Hierarchy of parsing exceptions.

After successful parsing of the *BPMN.Sharp* diagram into an *EssentialGraph*, a call to *GraphNormalization.Run(graph)* applies BPMN graph normalization, defined in the fourth section. As the result, an instance of *IntermediateGraph* is returned.

Finally, after normalization of the graph, a call to *Translator.Run(graph)* applies BPMN-to-IMDS translation rules according to the method proposed in the fourth section. As the result, an *IMDS.Model_S* is generated.

Additionally, the method `BPMN2IMDS.GetDeadlocks()` covers all the steps that `BPMN2IMDS.GetIMDS()` does but it also executes verification of the resulting instance of `IMDS.Model_S` using the `TempoRG` verifier and returns a list of `Deadlocks`. Figure 36 shows the class diagram of the class `Deadlock`. This class contains the following fields:

- `id` of type `String` – the identification string of the deadlock,
- `path` of type `List<DeadlockStep>` – the list of names of Sequence and Message Flows that led to the deadlock,
- `blockedElement` of type `BlockedElement` – an object containing information about the BPMN element which was verified to be blocked. It includes information which of its incoming flows were fired and which will remain dead.

Figure 36. Class diagram of `Deadlock`. Double arrows represent Collection Association.

6.3.2 Extension of *Dedan*

A new control button in the *Dedan* program has been added to load a BPMN diagram from file system. After clicking on the button with the BPMN logo in the upper, left corner of the main window of *Dedan*, user can select a `.bpmn` file to be uploaded. After selection of the diagram, `BPMN2IMDS.GetIMDS()` is executed and its result is displayed in the main window. User can now use all of the existing *Dedan* functionalities – like deadlock analysis or termination analysis – to check certain properties of the resulting IMDS model manually. Figure 37 shows the interface to the new functionality in the *Dedan* program.

Figure 37. Interface to the new functionality in Dedan.

6.3.3 *bpmn2imds-web*

Figure 38 shows the architecture of the *bpmn2imds-web* application. To begin with, the application is divided into two separate parts: *frontend* and *backend*. They both implement all use cases from Table 4. *Frontend* part is responsible for implementing use cases from for *BPMN visualization component* and *deadlock inspection component*. Backend part is responsible for implementing use cases for *BPMN verification component* and *BPMN-IMDS translation component*.

The frontend application was implemented in HTML and TypeScript using *Camunda Modeler*[29] and *Angular 7*[30]. *Camunda Modeler* was chosen as the tool to visualize BPMN diagrams, mainly because it is a mature, open-source BPMN tool which supports loading, visualization, editing and export of BPMN diagrams. It implements colors on BPMN diagrams in compliance with *BPMN Model Interchange* [31] standard, which enables marking deadlocks in color, export of the diagrams with marked deadlocks and import of them to other tool that support *BPMN Model Interchange*[32]. *Angular 7* is used as a wrapper around *Camunda Modeler*. It is the engine of the frontend interface. It handles all of the user interactions with the application.

The *frontend application* consists of three components: *verificationService* (*verification service*), *app* component and *editorService* (*editor service*). *Verification service* is responsible for communication with the application's backend via HTTP. It is called by the main component of the *frontend application* – called *app* – using *validate(k: number, p: RequestPayload)* method. This method takes as the first argument the desired parameterization of the BPMN-to-IMDS translation. The second argument contains a JSON structure, containing the BPMN in XML. The method calls the web service of the backend application, which is described in the following paragraphs.

Figure 38. Architecture of the web application *bpmn2imds-web*.

The *app* component is the core class of the *frontend application*. It is responsible for maintaining references to revealed deadlocks and handling user input.

The *editor service* is a wrapper around a *Camunda Modeler* – an open-source BPMN visualization tool, written in JavaScript. This component handles coloring of the BPMN elements, loading and exporting BPMN diagrams. It implements the *IBPMNEditor* interface (Table 5), which declares methods accessed by the *app* component that manipulate the BPMN diagram.

Table 5. *IBPMNEditor* interface.

method	purpose	returns	type
<i>getXmlString()</i>	get XML representation of the BPMN diagram	the string representation of the currently shown BPMN diagram	string
<i>loadXml(xml: string)</i>	visualize the diagram represented by the string in XML format	-	void
<i>setActiveDeadlock(id: string)</i>	sets the context of showing of the editor service to the deadlock with the given identification string.	-	void
<i>markFirst()</i>	used to trace the path of the deadlock	marks the beginning of the path to the deadlock	string
<i>markLast()</i>		marks the whole path to the deadlock	string
<i>markNext()</i>		marks the next step on the path to the deadlock	string
<i>markPrevious()</i>		marks the previous step on the path to the deadlock	string

<i>reset()</i>	reset colors on the diagram	-	void
<i>hasMoreSteps()</i>	helper functions	<i>true</i> if the current deadlock step is not the last	string
<i>hasLessSteps()</i>		<i>true</i> if the current deadlock step is not the first	string
<i>getDeadlockNumber()</i>		number of deadlocks	number

The interface between frontend and backend consists of a REST web service written using Web API .NET technology with one POST method: */validate/{n}*. The parameter *n* denotes the desired parametrization of the BPMN-to-IMDS translation.

The backend application consists of two components: Frontend Controller and Verification Controller. The first is used exclusively to host the frontend application. The second provides the *validate/{n}* REST endpoint.

The REST endpoint takes as the *n* parameter the parametrization of the BPMN-to-IMDS translation. As the request body, it accepts a JSON structure that contains XML representation of a given diagram. Then, the controller runs verification of the diagram, using an instance of the *BPMN2IMDS* class from *bpmn2imds-core*. As the response body, a JSON structure containing a string representation of deadlocks is returned.

In order to create instances of this class, during the setup of dependency injection using *Ninject*, the keyword *InRequestScope()* is used. This means, that a new instance of this class will be created for each request. It enables handling of concurrent requests by the backend application.

An example of the output generated by the frontend of *bpmn2imds-web* is presented on Figure 39. The BPMN diagram has been verified to contain a deadlock. The blocked BPMN element is marked with red, its dead Sequence Flows are marked also with red, while the Sequence Flows that were fired for the blocked element are marked with green. The remaining steps of the path that lead to the deadlock are marked with blue and enumerated.

Figure 39. Verification of BPMN diagrams using *bpmn2imds-web*.

7 Tests

7.1 *bpmn2imds-core*

The *bpmn2imds-core* component of the solution was tested thoroughly using unit and acceptance tests[33]. Unit tests are used to test low-level components of the software in an isolated manner; this includes tests of creation of vertices of the *EssentialGraph*, normalization of *EssentialGraph*, translation of *IntermediateGraph* into IMDS and verification if deadlocks are correctly revealed given an *IntermediateGraph*. Acceptance tests define the desired behavior of the software in term of deadlock detection. They test the software in the end-to-end manner. In case of *bpmn2imds-core* it means that each test case loads a BPMN file, executes deadlock verification on it and then check if deadlocks were found. Unit tests are implemented using *NUnit*[34]. Acceptance tests are implemented using *SpecFlow* [35].

7.1.1 Unit tests

Unit testing of *EssentialGraph* involves verification if its vertices are created with proper fields. An example test scenario involves creating *BPMN.Sharp* representation of a BPMN diagram, running generation of the corresponding *EssentialGraph* and then checking that a given vertex has correct identification string, is properly connected to the its neighbors etc. Each BPMN element – Start Event, End Event, Exclusive Gateway, Intermediate Event, Parallel Gateway and Activity – is tested using different scenarios, depending on their syntax. Those scenarios include for example nodes without incoming flows, nodes without outgoing flows, nodes with incident Message Flows and multiple incoming and outgoing flows.

Testing of graph normalization involves verification according to rules defined in the fourth section if the resulting *IntermediateGraph* contains correct vertices. To achieve that, a test scenario for each of the rows from Table 2 is created. An example includes checking if a Start Event with multiple outgoing Sequence Flows is correctly refactored to a construct corresponding to the Start Event with a Parallel Gateway attached to it. Additionally, tests for nodes that remain unchanged during normalization are implemented. Such a scenario includes for example checking if a Task with a single incoming and a single outgoing Sequence Flows remains unchanged in the normalized graph.

Unit tests of BPMN-to-IMDS translation involve creation of *IntermediateGraph* instances, execution of the translation procedure on them and then verification if the resulting IMDS model is correct. In particular, the tests ensure that *AND servers* and *Pool servers* are generated according to the rules proposed in the fourth section. This includes verification of generated services and states of servers and actions defined on servers.

Finally, unit testing of deadlock detection involves running verification of the created IMDS model with the *TempoRG* verifier. Instances of *IntermediateGraph* that correspond to a BPMN diagram containing a deadlock are created and then it is verified if their IMDS translation also contains a deadlock.

7.1.2 Acceptance tests

Acceptance tests are divided into four groups:

1. test scenarios that do not contain deadlocks,
2. test scenarios that contain deadlocks,
3. examples from literature.

The first group of tests aims to check if the software can handle deadlock-free diagrams. Because the process of translation consists of multiple steps, it is desired to check positive flow of its execution. Scenarios tested here include diagrams with loops, diagrams containing Parallel Gateways, etc.

The second group of tests aims to check if the *bpmn2imds-core* actually finds deadlocks on ill-structured diagrams. For example, it is tested that an Exclusive Gateway paired with a Parallel Gateway constitutes a deadlock.

The third group of tests contains examples from the literature, including BPMN samples proposed by the authors of *VBPMN* [20][21].

7.2 *bpmn2imds-web*

The backend part of *bpmn2imds-web* is tested using integration and concurrency tests[33]. Integration tests ensure that the *validate/{n}* endpoint of the WEB API controller always responses meaningfully. Concurrency tests check if the controller can handle many requests simultaneously. Integration tests are implemented in *NUnit*[34], while concurrency tests are implemented using the tool *JMeter*[36]. The frontend part of *bpmn2imds-web* was tested manually.

7.2.1 Frontend application

Because the frontend part of *bpmn2imds-web* is a one-page application, it was tested only manually. The functionalities checked manually include:

- visualization of deadlocks on BPMN diagrams,
- selection of the inspected deadlock from the drop-down menu,
- tracing paths of deadlocks using “*Step forward*”, “*Step backward*”, “*Last step*” and “*First step*” buttons,
- resetting colors on the diagram,
- exporting the diagram with a marked deadlock to a file,
- setting the parametrization of the BPMN-to-IMDS verification using the drop-down menu,
- creation of sequence diagrams for deadlocks.

7.2.2 Integration tests

Integration tests are divided into two groups: test scenarios with positive flow of execution and test scenarios with negative flow of execution. The former include tests of BPMN-to-IMDS translation’s

parameterization and tests if the controller correctly sends lists of deadlocks. The tests of negative flow check if a request with an invalid body is translated into meaningful responses. Test scenarios in this case include requests with:

- empty or invalid JSON structure of the request body,
- empty or invalid XML field that represents a BPMN diagram in the request body,
- correct request body, but unsupported BPMN elements on the diagram.

7.2.3 Concurrency tests

Concurrency tests verify if the *validate/{n}* endpoint of the WEB API controller can handle concurrent requests. To check this, JMeter[36], a tool to test performance of HTTP interfaces, is used. In the case of *bpmn2imds-web*, JMeter is used to send concurrently 100 HTTP requests to the *validate/{n}* endpoint. It is checked that the responses during such a test are consistent with the expected values and no errors possibly connected with concurrency are returned.

8 Summary

8.1 Conclusion

The main goal of this thesis was to propose a translation of Business Process Collaboration and Process Diagrams into Integrated Model of Distributed Systems. In order to achieve this, syntax and semantics were defined for BPMN Process and Collaboration Diagrams. Afterwards, a method of normalization and translation of BPMN diagrams into IMDS specifications was introduced. The authors intention was to develop a general method of such translation, ie. with as few syntactical constraints as possible for the modeled subset of BPMN elements.

The syntax proposed for BPMN is formulated in terms of graph theory. A special type of edges, called Boundary Links, is introduced in order to formalize Boundary Event handling. The proposed semantics is characterized by *locality* – that is, semantics of each of those elements depends only on other elements, that they are directly connected to. During translation, the given BPMN diagrams is refactored into another semantically equivalent diagram in order to achieve consistence of activation and execution semantics. The second step of translation transforms each of the node of the normalized diagram into an IMDS component. As a result, an IMDS specification of the given BPMN model is returned.

One of the limitations of the proposed method is that it cannot handle diagrams which are unbounded – that is, for which exists a flow that can accumulate infinitely many tokens. This problem stems from the nature of IMDS and cannot be solved by any improvement to the translation method. If the BPMN diagram is bounded, detection of partial deadlocks in its corresponding IMDS specification reveals correctly structural flaws, given that a proper parametrization for the translation method has been used. On the other hand, due to the need to preallocate agents, the state space of the resulting IMDS models tend to be huge, which slows down the process of its analysis.

Another limitation is that the translation method does not consider BPMN elements with non-local semantics. In order to achieve this, the proposed semantics of BPMN must be extended.

The second goal of this thesis – development of an automatic tool to verify BPMN diagrams and visualize deadlocks – has been achieved for the proposed subset of BPMN. In comparison to other tools, such as [9] and [12], the tool enables visualization of diagrams. Additionally, in comparison to [18], the developed tool enables step-by-step simulation of a revealed deadlock and a sequence diagram is generated per each deadlock.

8.2 Future work

As far as the subset of BPMN considered in this thesis is concerned, attempts are being made to develop a method of translation of Flow Objects not covered in this thesis, in particular Event-based Gateways and Inclusive Gateways. Those attempts were only partially successful in the case of Event-based Gateways and unsuccessful in the case of Inclusive Gateways. The former have local semantics, but in

comparison to other elements with such semantics, they cannot be as easily translated into IMDS. To achieve this, creation of a new set of IMDS agents of purely technical nature has to be introduced in the translation method. Their purpose is to reset the gateway each time an Intermediate Event bound to the gateway occurs. Attempts are being made to implement the translation of Event-based Gateways in the next version of the *bpmn2imds* utility.

In case of Inclusive Gateways, and more generally elements with non-local semantics, the proposed formalization of BPMN must be extended in order to correctly mimic their behavior.

Another possible improvement to the proposed translation method is to parametrize it not per a BPMN diagram, like in the case of the parameter K , but rather per a single BPMN element instead. The idea is to analyze how many times a given BPMN can be visited in order to determine how many agents need to be preallocated on its translation. This would involve analysis of possible self-loops for Parallel Gateways and general reachability analysis for Start Events. Introducing such granularity to the parametrization of the proposed BPMN-to-IMDS translation method would help to reduce space growth, introduced by preallocation of agents.

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Index of symbols and abbreviations

BPMN – Business Process Model and Notation
IMDS – Integrated Model of Distributed Systems
UML – Unified Modeling Language

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